

Project Management/Deliverable 1.1

WP1. Project Management and Coordination Activities, T1.1-Project Coordination, Quality Assurance and Risk Management, T1.2-Administrative & Financial Coordination.

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Technical references

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1 Table of contents

1	Table of contents.....	3
2	List of abbreviations	5
3	Executive Summary	6
4	Introduction	7
5	Project Management.....	8
5.1	Management Structure	8
5.2	Role of the bodies	9
5.2.1	Project Coordinator.....	9
5.2.2	General Assembly (GA)	10
5.2.3	Project Management Board (PMB).....	12
5.2.4	Work Package Leaders and Tasks Leaders. Work Package Management	14
5.3	ANIPH Meetings	16
5.4	Project monitoring	17
5.4.1	ANIPH internal monitoring.....	18
5.4.2	ANIPH official monitoring	21
5.5	Project deliverables.....	24
5.5.1	General elaboration rules	25
5.5.2	Deliverable quality assurance	25
6	ANIPH online repository	28
7	ANIPH online work management system	31
8	Other relevant information	35
9	Conclusions	36
10	References	37
11	Annexes.....	38

List of Tables

<i>Table 1. PHAntastic General Assembly members.</i>	10
<i>Table 2. Tentative General Assembly meetings plan.</i>	11
<i>Table 3. ANIPH Work Packages Leaders and Tasks Leaders</i>	14
<i>Table 4. General operational procedures for ANIPH governance bodies.</i>	16

List of Figures

<i>Figure 1. ANIPH Management structure.</i>	8
<i>Figure 2. ANIPH internal information flow.</i>	18
<i>Figure 3. ANIPH internal information flow.</i>	21
<i>Figure 4. ANIPH deliverables review process.</i>	25
<i>Figure 5. ANIPH project Online Repository folders.</i>	28
<i>Figure 6. ANIPH WPs folder content.</i>	29
<i>Figure 7. ANIPH templates and logos folder content.</i>	29
<i>Figure 8. ANIPH official documents folder content.</i>	30
<i>Figure 9. ANIPH Monday platform structure</i>	31
<i>Figure 10. ANIPH DOA dashboard structure on Monday.</i>	32
<i>Figure 11. Overview to the structure at WP level.</i>	32
<i>Figure 12. Overview to the structure at deliverables level.</i>	33
<i>Figure 13. Overview to the structure at objectives level.</i>	33
<i>Figure 14. Overview to the structure at milestones level.</i>	33
<i>Figure 15. Overview of the structure at risks level.</i>	34
<i>Figure 16. Overview of the deliverables review plan.</i>	34

2 List of abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
DoA	Description of the Action
GA	General Assembly
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
PC	Project Coordinator
PFSIGN	Project Financial Signatory
PLSIGN	Project Legal Signatory
PMB	Project Management Board
PM ²	P-M squared
SDGs	Sustainable development goals
TC	Technical Coordinator
WP	Work Package

3 Executive Summary

Deliverable 1.1 “Project Management” presents a guideline for the ANIPH project management, as a part of the activities in WP1. The objective of this guideline is to establish and describe the methodology, procedures, and activities of planning, organizing, securing, monitoring, and managing the resources and work necessary to deliver the specific project goals and objectives in an effective and efficient way.

This guideline aims to facilitate the interactions between the partners during the project implementation by providing internal procedures adapted to European Commission rules.

Deliverable 1.1 describes the quality plan for ANIPH, including the following information:

- ✓ The governance management structures, and the role of the bodies. The organizational structure and decision-taking mechanisms will support the consortium in its day-to-day activities.
- ✓ The management processes to be implemented to ensure efficiency, transparency, and accountability, including templates for reporting, and planned meetings.
- ✓ The quality control system that will be applied to all project deliverables and activities, and monitoring and evaluation mechanisms.
- ✓ The communication procedures that will be established to ensure fluid and effective communication among all stakeholders.

Deliverable 1.1 also includes a chapter on project repository and the software used for the project management. The internal information flows established ensure that all the partners are informed about the project progress and make the project results easily available.

In addition to this deliverable 1.1, the ANIPH project will be guided by other reference documents that define the legal procedures, and the project work programme: the Grant Agreement, Annex I-DoA parts A and B, Consortium Agreement. These documents are available on the ANIPH Google Drive repository.

4 Introduction

This Project Management Guideline and Quality Plan is based on PM2 methodology, a Project Management Methodology developed by the European Commission. It has been tailored to be applied for ANIPH Project, according to the Project's specific needs, and will cover the execution phase of the Project. This deliverable comprises the activities and procedures for ANIPH Project Management and Quality Assurance.

ANIPH is a forty-eight-months project whose work plan is broken down into thirteen work-packages, which are also broken down into several tasks, including as well eight Milestones scheduled during the life cycle of the project, as explained in detail in the project DoA document. ANIPH Consortium is formed by eight complementary partners from five European countries and one partner from Canada, covering the entire value chain.

5 Project Management

This section describes the project management elements, structure and procedures that aim at ensuring the successful completion of the project's objectives. This chapter defines in detail the governance structure, establishes the contact details of the key consortium staff, and describes the model for monitoring the Project by setting up auto-control mechanisms. The chapter also describes the documentation processes in terms of templates, flow of information and structure of the Deliverables.

5.1 Management Structure

The consortium organizational and management structure was decided during the planning phase of the Project and is described in detail in the CA, according to different bodies and management positions and responsibilities.

This organizational structure is shown in Figure 1

Figure 1. ANIPH Management structure.

The ANIPH governance structure includes the following bodies of the project:

- The General Assembly (GA).
- Project Management Board (PMB).

The coordination and management activities of the project (WP1 & 7) are performed by the Project Coordinator, which is the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the partners of the project and the Funding Authority, in cooperation with interacting bodies GA and PMB.

The work is organised into Work Packages, led by Work Package Leaders, who coordinate, plan, monitor and report to the Project Management Board about WP progress at least every quarter, during fixed time slot conference calls. Each Work Package is split in different tasks including all the planned activities to achieve the expected objectives to achieve.

5.2 Role of the bodies

5.2.1 Project Coordinator

The Coordinator will be the intermediary between the partners and REA and shall perform all tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. The responsibilities of the Coordinator includes:

- Monitor the compliance by the partners with their obligations, and the proper project implementation.
- Request and review any documents or information required by REA.
- Submit the deliverables and reports to REA.
- Ensure that all payments are made to the other beneficiaries.
- Ensure on a daily basis the communication between the different partners (notably by implementing collaborative platform, being responsible for official meetings organizations).
- Transmitting promptly documents and information connected with the Project to any other Party concerned.

In ANIPH project the Project Coordinator is a figure of management composed of a team that develops their responsibility according to this distribution of the work:

-Primary Project coordinator. -Carmen Fernández Ayuso (CETEC). General responsible for the ANIPH project coordination and in charge of the coordination of WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7, WP8, WP9, WP10, WP11, WP12 and WP13.

-Secondary Project Coordinator. Juan Agüera (CETEC). In charge of the financial coordination of WP1 and WP7.

5.2.2 General Assembly (GA)

The General Assembly is the **ultimate decision-making and conflict resolution body of the Consortium**. It will consist of one representative of each partner. The coordinator shall chair all meetings.

Table 1. PHAntastic General Assembly members.

Organisation	Person
CETEC	Carmen Fernández
	Juan Agüera
CETBIO	María Nicolás
AUA	Chrysanthos Maraveas
	Marianna Kotzabasaki
TVB	William Bardosh
UGR	Juan Antonio Marchal
	Ana Voltés Martínez
	Elisa Nygren Jiménez
	José Manuel Domínguez
GOPHA	Rick passenier
	Maximilian Lackner
KVC	Maite Ferrando
ICONS	Marcello Bardellini
	Chiara Serio

The GA has decision-making power with respect to non-operational, strategic, and long-term issues, however it shall be free to act on its own initiative to formulate proposals and take decisions in accordance with the procedures set out in the CA. In addition, all proposals made by the Project Management Board shall also be considered and decided upon by the General Assembly. The tasks of the GA include:

- Assessment of the progress of the project and resources.
- Changes of the work programme and its timing.
- Agreeing on external opportunities.
- Changes of Grant Agreement and technical annex.

- Modifications to attachments of the Consortium Agreement (background, third parties for simplified transfer, additions to identified affiliated entities).

The following decisions shall be taken by the General Assembly:

- Content, finances, and intellectual property rights.
- Evolution of the consortium and changes.
- Appointment of the Project Management Board.
- Proposals for changes to Annexes 1 and 2 of the Grant Agreement to be agreed by the Funding Authority.
- Modifications to Attachment 1 of the Consortium Agreement (Background Included).
- Additions to Attachment 2 of the Consortium Agreement (Accession document).
- Additions to Attachment 3 of the Consortium Agreement (List of Third Parties for simplified transfer).

Planned meetings:

- Ordinary meetings (every 6 months).
- Extraordinary meetings (at any time upon written request of any member).

The Project Coordinator shall chair all meetings of the General Assembly.

Table 2. Tentative General Assembly meetings plan.

Meeting n ^o .	Expected date	Organiser
GA1	January 2025	CETEC
GA2	July 2025	KVC
GA3	January 2026	CETEC
GA4	July 2026	GOPHA
GA5	January 2027	CETBIO
GA6	July 2027	UGR
GA7	January 2028	AUA
GA8	July 2028	ICONS
GA9	December 2028	CETEC

Table 2, shows a preliminary plan for the General Assembly meetings. It can be adapted according to the partners and project needs.

5.2.3 Project Management Board (PMB)

Project Management Board as the **supervisory body for the execution of the Project** which shall report to and be accountable to the General Assembly.

The Project Management Board shall consist of the Coordination Board (Project Coordinator, Technical Manager, Exploitation & Dissemination & Communication Manager, SSbD & Ethic Manage) and the Work Packages Leaders.

The Coordination Board is composed by the following positions of responsibility:

- Project Coordinator (CETEC). Project Coordination Team: Carmen Fernández and Juan Agüera.
- Technical Manager (AUA). In charge of WP2-WP4 and WP8-10. Chrysanthos Maraveas & Marianna Kotzabasaki
- Exploitation & Dissemination & Communication Manager (ICONS). In charge of WP6 and WP12. Marcello Bardellini.
- SSbD and Ethic Manager (KVC). In charge of WP5, WP11 and WP13. Maite Ferrando & Alba Matamoros

The WP leaders is composed by the following positions of responsibility:

- CETEC-WP1; Carmen Fernández.
- CETEC-WP2; Jean David Peltier
- CETBIO-WP3; María Nicolás and Salvador García
- UGR-WP4; Juan Antonio Marchal Corrales & JM Domínguez-Vera
- KVC-WP5; Maite Ferrando & Alba Matamoros
- ICONS-WP6; Marcello Bardellini & Chiara Serio
- CETEC-WP7; Carmen Fernández
- UGR-WP8; Juan Antonio Marchal Corrales & José Manuel Dominguez Vera
- AUA-WP9; Chrysanthos Maraveas & Marianna Kotzabasaki
- UGR-WP10; Juan Antonio Marchal Corrales & José Manuel Dominguez Vera
- KVC-WP11; Maite Ferrando & Alba Matamoros

- ICONS-WP12; Marcello Bardellini & Chiara Serio
- CETEC-WP13; Carmen Fernández

The Project Coordinator shall chair all meetings of the Project Management Board.

The ANIPH managers (Technical Manager, Exploitation & Dissemination & Communication Manager, SSbD and Ethics Manager) will support the Coordinator and the WP leaders according to their areas of expertise:

- Follow up of the corresponding project activities and their proper implementation.
- Support the corresponding WP leaders to ensure the quality of the project.
- Review the corresponding deliverables and milestones.
- Follow up the risk assessment.
- Analysis of needs and opportunities.
- Support in the preparation of the Project Management Board.
- Support in the preparation of periodic report.

Contact details of all ANIPH partners are available on the ANIPH Online Repository (see section 5) and ANIPH Online Work Flow Management (see section 6)

The Project Management Board will be responsible for the proper execution and implementation of the decisions of the General Assembly. It will monitor the effective and efficient implementation of the Project. In particular the responsibilities of the PMB will be:

- Assessment of the implementation of the decisions of the General Assembly.
- Monitor the effective and efficient implementation of the project.
- Support the coordinator in preparing the meetings, propose decisions and prepare the agenda of the General Assembly.
- Seek a consensus among the Parties without losing track of the progress of the Project as per the Consortium Plan.
- Collect information at least quarterly on the progress of the Project, examine that information to assess the compliance of the Project with the Consortium Plan and, if necessary, propose modifications of the Consortium Plan to the General Assembly.
- Support the Coordinator in preparing meetings with the Granting Authority and in

preparing related data and reports.

- Advise the GA on ways to rearrange tasks and budgets of the Parties concerned in the case of abolished tasks as a result of a decision of the GA. Such rearrangement shall take into consideration any prior legitimate commitments which cannot be cancelled.

- Risks management plan and monitoring.

- Innovation management.

Planned meetings:

- Ordinary meetings (Quarterly).

- Extraordinary meetings (at any time upon written request of any member).

The Project Coordinator shall chair all meetings of the Coordination Board.

5.2.4 Work Package Leaders and Tasks Leaders. Work Package Management

The ANIPH Project is split into 13 Work Packages (WP), including different Tasks (T). A Work Package leader and a Task leader are appointed to coordinate each WP and Task, respectively. The initial leader organizations are listed below. The complete list including the names of the leaders and their contact details is regularly updated on the ANIPH SharePoint and project management software.

Table 3. ANIPH Work Packages Leaders and Tasks Leaders

WP/Task	Lead Organisation	Personnel Responsible
WP1	CETEC	Carmen Fernández
T1.1	CETEC	Carmen Fernández
T1.2	CETEC	Juan Agüera
T1.3	KVC	Alba Matamoros
WP2	CETEC	Jean David Peltier
T2.1	CETEC	Jean David Peltier
T2.2	GOPHA	Rick Passenier
T2.3	KVC	Alba Matamoros
T2.4	CETEC	Jean David Peltier
T2.5	AUA	Marianna Kotzabasaki & Chrysanthos Maraveas
WP3	CETBIO	María Nicolás
T3.1	CETBIO	María Nicolás
T3.2	CETEC	Jean David Peltier
T3.3	AUA	Marianna Kotzabasaki & Chrysanthos Maraveas

T3.4	CETEC	Jean David Peltier
WP4	UGR	Juan Antonio Marchal Corrales & JM Dominguez-Vera
T4.1	UGR	Juan Antonio Marchal Corrales & JM Dominguez-Vera
T4.2	TVB	Ray Bergstra
T4.3	AUA	Marianna Kotzabasaki & Chrysanthos Maraveas
WP5	KVC	Maite Ferrnado & Alba Matamoros
T5.1	CETEC	Jaime Ortiz
T5.2	AUA	Marianna Kotzabasaki & Chrysanthos Maraveas
T5.3	KVC	Alba Matamoros
T5.4	GOPHA	Rick Passenier
WP6	ICONS	Marcello Bardellini & Chiara Serio
T6.1	ICONS	Chiara Serio
T6.2	ICONS	Chiara Serio
T6.3	KVC	Alba Matamoros
T6.4	KVC	Alba Matamoros
T6.5	CETEC	Carmen Fernández Ayuso
T6.6	ICONS	Claudia Crippa
WP7	CETEC	Carmen Fernández
T7.1	CETEC	Carmen Fernández
T7.2	CETEC	Juan Agüera
T7.3	KVC	Alba Matamoros
WP8	UGR	Juan Antonio Marchal Corrales & José Manuel Dominguez Vera
T8.1	UGR	Juan Antonio Marchal Corrales
T8.2	TVB	Ray Bergstra
T8.3	UGR	Juan Antonio Marchal Corrales
T8.4	AUA	Marianna Kotzabasaki & Chrysanthos Maraveas
WP9	AUA	Chrysanthos Maraveas & Marianna Kotzabasaki
T9.1	AUA	Marianna Kotzabasaki & Chrysanthos Maraveas
T9.2	CETEC	Jean-David Pielter
WP10	UGR	Juan Antonio Marchal Corrales & José Manuel Dominguez Vera
T10.1	CETBIO	María Nicolás
T10.2	UGR	Juan Antonio Marchal Corrales
WP11	KVC	Maite Ferrado & Alba Matamoros
T11.1	CETEC	Jaime Ortiz
T11.2	AUA	Marianna Kotzabasaki & Chrysanthos Maraveas
T11.3	KVC	Alba Matamoros
T11.4	GOPHA	Rick Passenier
WP12	ICONS	Marcello Bardellini & Chiara Serio
T12.1	ICONS	Chiara Serio
T12.2	KVC	Alba Matamoros
T12.3	KVC	Alba Matamoros

T12.4	ICONS	Andrea Valeri
WP13	CETEC	Carmen Fernández

The WP leader and the Task leaders will have the following responsibilities:

- Monitor the effective and efficient implementation of the activities that they lead.
- Collect information about the activities carried out and inform to the coordinator and the corresponding ANIPH managers about the advancements.
- Communicate actively with the WP team and with the coordinator.
- Organise periodic meetings with the WP team to assess the progress.
- Inform the Coordinator about any issue or change occurred, and propose possible fallback scenarios in case of major deviations from the work plan that have an impact on the objectives or the work packages and/or the project.
- Knowledge management.
- Formulate an implementation plan for the activities within the WP for coming periods.
- Support the Coordinator in preparing related data and reports.

5.3 ANIPH Meetings

This section details the main operating procedures of the governance bodies. All detailed rules and procedures are included in the CA approved by all members of the consortium.

Table 4. General operational procedures for ANIPH governance bodies.

	General Assembly (GA)	Project management Board (PMB)
Ordinary meeting	At least twice a year	At least quarterly
Extraordinary meeting	At any time upon written request of the Project Management Board or 1/3 of the Members of the General Assembly	At any time upon written request of any Member of the Project Management Board
Participants	One representative person (at least) from each partner	One representative person (at least) from each member

Notice of a meeting	45 calendar days for an ordinary meeting, and 15 days for an extraordinary meeting	14 calendar days for an ordinary meeting, and 7 days for an extraordinary meeting
Sending the agenda	21 calendar days for an ordinary meeting, and 10 calendar days for an extraordinary meeting.	7 calendar days for both
Adding agenda items	14 calendar days for an ordinary meeting, and 7 calendar days for an extraordinary meeting	2 calendar days for both

The Project Coordinator is responsible for sending the agenda for the meetings and for elaborate the minutes of meetings.

Concerning voting rules, each Governance Body shall not deliberate and decide validly unless two-thirds (2/3) of its members are present or represented (quorum).

If the *quorum* is not reached, the chairperson shall convene another ordinary meeting within 15 calendar days. If the quorum is not reached in this meeting, the chairperson shall convene an extraordinary meeting which shall be entitled to decide by majority even if less than the quorum of members is present or represented.

Each member of a Consortium Body present or represented in the meeting shall have one vote.

5.4 Project monitoring

The Project Coordinator is the ultimate body for the right monitoring and control of the project. To do this a Cyclical Quality Assurance scheme (Planning—Realization—Analysis—Revision) will be used.

This cyclical approach will enable the consortium, specially the PMB, to monitor costs, time and quality of ANIPH project.

- Costs means that tasks are completed withing the budget assigned in the Gant Agreement.
- Time means that milestones, deliverables and official reports are available on time.
- Quality means that the results reach the project objectives.

5.4.1 ANIPH internal monitoring

5.4.1.1 ANIPH Internal information flows

This section describes the bottom-up and top-down communication flows in ANIPH project. The ANIPH internal bottom-up information flow facilitates the project's progress by continuously exchanging information with the Project Consortium and supporting the completion of assigned work. To do this it will be performed at three different levels:

- Information at task level by the Task leader.
- Information at WP level by the WP leader.
- Information at Project level by the Project Management Board and the Coordinator.

The main tools for the ANIPH project monitoring are the deliverables. The information necessary to complete these deliverables and the rest of the information required by the European Commission will be compiled following the process, templates and times described in the following Figure 2.

Figure 2. ANIPH internal information flow.

In ANIPH each WP leader is responsible for the WP and its tasks, including a sufficient effort/calendar control; and coordination, both internally and with other WPs, as well as the planning and periodicity of the WPs-reports (from the partners to the Task leader using the Partner activities template; and, from the Task leader to the WP leader using the task status report).

WP leaders, based on the information collected through the Task status reports as described above, will prepare a WP progress report (using the template called WP status report) that they will send monthly to the corresponding ANIPH manager and to the Project Coordinator team (quarterly), specifically:

- Technical Manager. In charge of WP2, WP3, WP4, WP9, WP9, WP10. Chrysanthos Maraveas & Marianna Kotzabasaki (AUA).
- Exploitation & Dissemination & Communication Manager. In charge of WP6 and WP12. Marcello Bardellini. (ICONS).
- SSbD and Ethic Manager. In charge of WP5, WP11 and WP13. Alba Matamoros (KVC)

The Project Coordination Team:

- Carmen Fernández (CETEC). In charge of the coordination of WP1 and WP7.
- Juan Agüera (CETEC). In charge of the of the financial coordination of WP1 and WP7.

In a complementary way, all partners are responsible to communicate the potential issues and/or changes detected. In particular all SSbD and Ethic management will be managed by KVC.

To do this, they must inform the corresponding ANIPH Manager when the issue/change is detected and also include this information in their periodic report through the Partner activities template.

On the other hand, as shown in the figure 2, the WP leaders 15 days before the Periodic Report (months 24 and 48) will elaborate a summary report of the activities developed in their WP, using the template named WP summary report. This report will be revised by the corresponding ANIPH manager and will be sent to the Project Coordination responsible.

Furthermore, all the ANIPH meeting decisions, agreements, or discussions will be registered through minutes (minutes meeting template). These minutes will be uploaded on the ANIPH platform once it will be accepted by all participants. To do it, the chairperson (Task leader, WP leader, ANIPH Manager, or Project Coordinator) will elaborate and send a draft to all participants. The minutes shall be considered accepted if, within 15 calendar days from sending, no participant has sent an objection in writing to the chairperson with respect to the accuracy of the draft of the minutes.

In case of a relevant change required in the project, the partner requesting the change will send the information to the Coordination team through the Change request form template.

More information about ANIPH templates in section 5.

Regarding the ANIPH internal top-down information flow will be deployed by direct communication through the Project Coordinator Team. To do this conventional communication channels could be used as email (coordination@aniph.org), telephone (CETEC's phone +34968632200), or during the ANIPH meetings.

5.4.1.2 ANIPH process for implementing corrective actions.

The process for implementing corrective actions is based on the ANIPH internal information process (described in section 4.4.1.1 of this document), and the official reporting processes (continuous reporting and periodic reporting).

In this document corrective action is an action aimed at removing the cause of product issues or unwanted deviations in order to prevent their future recurrence.

When a ANIPH partner detects an issue, deviation and/or change, this will be communicated in accordance with the process described in section 4.4.1.1. After receiving the information, the ANIPH Manager (corresponding to the affected WP) will be able to:

- If the issue or deviation is operational and only affects one WP. The ANIPH manager will inform the WP leader who, after analyzing the deviation or issue, will apply the corrective action(s) necessary to solve it. The entire process will be recorded in the corresponding monthly report (WP status report) of the WP.
- If the issue or deviation is operational and affects more than one WP. The ANIPH manager together with the leaders of the affected WPs will agree and adopt the appropriate actions to solve the issue or deviation in a consensual manner. The entire process will be recorded in the corresponding monthly report (WP status report) of the WP (s).
- If the issue or deviation is strategic. The ANIPH manager will inform the Project coordinator team and the WP leader(s) involved, and a corrective plan will be jointly developed. If, in the opinion of the Project Coordinator, the issue or deviation is significant, an Extraordinary PMB Meeting will be convened; otherwise, it will be evaluated at the scheduled ordinary meetings.

The PMB, after evaluating the issue or deviation, is the one who decides whether or not to involve the GA.

In this document, an operational issue or deviation is understood to be one that does not modify the objective of the Task or Work Package and also has no effect on compliance with the ANIPH monitoring variables (quality, time and cost). In this sense strategic issue or deviation is that are not operational.

5.4.2 ANIPH official monitoring

In Horizon Europe projects there's two types of reporting:

- Continuous Reporting: available from the beginning of a project.
- Periodic Reporting: available at the end of a reporting period.

Figure 3. ANIPH internal information flow.

5.4.2.1 ANIPH continuous reporting

The continuous reporting is available from the beginning of the project (1st of January 2025) in the Grant Management services in the Funding & Tenders Portal (<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/home>).

The contents that must be included in this module are (for informational purposes only):

- **Project Summary** including information about context and overall objectives, work performed and main achievements, Results beyond the state of the art, and Policy relevant evidence of your project
- **Researches Involved in the Project.** Data (information on the researcher) originally included in the Grant Agreement are available for editing via the Continuous Reporting.

- **Deliverables.** Online repository for uploading the Project Deliverables.
- **Milestones.** Online tool to report on the achievement of Milestones.
- **Critical Risks.** Critical implementation risks and mitigation actions for foreseen risks and unforeseen risks.
- **Publications.** Online tool to cover the publications linked to the Project including suggested publications from OpenAIRE (a list of publications retrieved directly from OpenAire and linked to the Project) and Project Publications (publications linked to the Project and that have been imported by the Consortium).
- **Results.** A results questionnaire including information about results and results ownership.
- **Dissemination Activities.** Dissemination questionnaire that concerns the public disclosure of the Project results via dissemination activities by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including the scientific publications in any medium.
- **Communications Activities.** Communications Activities questionnaire lists all communication activities for the Project.
- **Standards.** Standards questionnaire including information about: Definition of standardization activities; Description of a given standardization activities and reference to the relevant group; Types of standardization bodies involved; Names of standardization bodies involved; Reference to an existing Standard (if available).
- **Intellectual Property Rights (IPR).** Online tool to inform about IPR of the Project (add IPR, editing IPR and deleting IPR).
- **Datasets.** Datasets questionnaire for informing about Open Science requirements including Datasets suggested by OpenAIRE (a list of available datasets retrieved directly from OpenAire and linked to the Project. Each record can then be imported to the Project Datasets or discarded); and Project Datasets (shows the datasets linked to the Project and that have been imported by the Consortium).
- **Impact.** Impact questionnaire including information about: Technology readiness; Sustainable Development Goal (SDGs); and Overall Citizen engagement.

- **Impact Continuation.** Impact questionnaire including information about: scientific; societal; environmental; economic impact(s) resulting from the Project's implementation.
- **Other results.** Other Results questionnaire for including a list of the Project results other than those included in the Results tab.

The continuous reporting tool is available in a collaborative way (all ANIPH partners can edit). However, in order to guarantee the quality of the information, **only the Project Coordination Team of ANIPH will complete this information.**

5.4.2.2 ANIPH periodic reporting

ANIPH consortium must officially report the Project's progress together with all eligible costs after each reporting period in its **Periodic Report**. Periods are:

- RP1: from M1 to M24
- RP2: from M25 to M48

Periodic Reports include a technical report and a financial report.

Completing the technical part includes the following (for informational purposes only):

- Part A – The Project Coordination Team will update the tables on an ongoing basis in the continuous reporting module. The information in the tables is then automatically compiled to create part A.
- Part B – Will be prepared outside the grant management tool, using the official template. When done, it will be saved as a single PDF file and uploaded to the (Funding and Tenders portal) grant management system.

Due to the limited timeframe, a 60 days slot, for preparing both reports (technical and financial), it shall be imperative that all partners provide the Financial Coordinator with a preliminary financial report outlining expected costs for each reporting period no later than 15 days before the periodic report starts.

The financial report includes a financial statement, an explanation on the use of resources, and a request for payment. Completing the financial statement includes different steps:

- All beneficiaries will fill in their own financial statement, electronically sign it and submit it to the Project Coordinator. No financial statement submitted shall be included in the periodic report without the favourable opinion of the Financial Coordinator to the above-mentioned preliminary financial report.
- Users who can fill in the statement include the Participant Contacts, Project Financial Signatories, Task Managers, but only the Project Financial Signatory (PFSIGN) can electronically sign and submit the statement. For this reason, all partners will make sure they have assigned an FSIGN user to ANIPH in their organization.

The Project Coordinator may decide to submit the report without a financial statement from certain partners (e.g., if a beneficiary cannot submit its individual financial statement on time) therefore those costs would not be considered for that particular interim payment.

5.4.2.3 ANIPH financial preliminary reports

An internal financial reporting procedure has been established to provide the coordinator with the individual costs of each partner to ensure an accurate financial development of the project. The main objective of this procedure is to detect potential financial issues that may jeopardise the project's technical development. Additionally, this procedure will help both the partners and the coordinator gather all the necessary financial information in a timely manner to smoothly complete the respective periodic reports.

These preliminary internal reports will be requested from each partner and should be sent to the coordinator 20 days before each General Assembly.

To facilitate this task, a template will be shared with each beneficiary to be filled with their respective costs.

5.5 Project deliverables

The Deliverables are the main tools for both internal monitoring and official monitoring of the ANIPH project. Deliverable submission is an obligation for all beneficiaries according to the Grant Agreement. The Project Coordinator is responsible for submitting all deliverables at their due date

according to the List of Deliverables (see DoA, Part A).

5.5.1 General elaboration rules

The deliverables will be prepared according to the Deliverable Template (see ANIPH Online Repository), in compliance with its format, logos, statements and disclaimers.

In the phase of Deliverable elaboration, the following rules have to be taken into consideration:

- Objectives have to be clear from the beginning.
- The document has to be concise: giving a lot of information clearly and in a few words; expressing what needs to be said without unnecessary words; avoiding useless lengthening.
- Synthesize, summarize and include an appropriate level of details, being clear.
- To avoid repeating contents already described in previous Deliverables or in the Grant Agreement (always use references for that).
- Any bibliographic citation has to be referenced, using a numeric type of citation such as IEEE.

The size for a given Deliverable depends largely on the topic and the objectives. Annexes may be added.

5.5.2 Deliverable quality assurance

In order to ensure the availability on time and the quality of the ANIPH deliverables, a specific process for checking its quality has been established. This process is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 4. ANIPH deliverables review process.

To implement this process, a Plan to review Deliverables has been elaborated including for each Deliverable described in the DoA:

Deliverable responsible: partner, person in charge, and contact data (email and telephone number).

Deliverable reviewer: reviewer partner, person in charge, and contact data (email and telephone number).

Timelines: 1st Due Date (Responsible send to the Reviewer 1), 2nd Due Date (Reviewer 1 sends back to the Responsible), 3th Due Date (Responsible sends to the Reviewer 2), 4th Due Date (Reviewer 2 sends back to the Responsible), 5th Due Date (Responsible send to the Coordination Team) and Final Due Date (Coordination Team send to the European Commission).

This Plan is available in the ANIPH Google Drive Repository (see section 5, [ANIPH Deliverables Review Plan](#)) and ANIPH Online Work Flow Management Platform (see section 6, [Monday ANIPH Deliverables Review Plan](#)).

The outcome of the review process will not be reflected in any formal document for avoiding any more bureaucratic burdens, but the partners involved in the process will take into account the following two criteria:

- Scientific criteria

Relevance: How relevant for the Project are the topics included, and more specifically for the WP producing the Deliverable? This question refers to the relevance of contents according to the Project objectives and the WP's specific objectives.

Completeness: Have all the topics of the Deliverable been properly covered? This question refers not only to the scope of the Deliverable but also to relevant aspects according to the scientific and technical requirements from other WPs in ANIPH that are susceptible to be affected by the contents of this Deliverable.

Appropriate level of detail: Is there an appropriate level of detail in the analysis of each element? This question refers to providing sufficient information so that all statements, claims,

descriptions and conclusions are either self-evident or adequately and scientifically articulated. All information should have the depth needed for the purpose of the document.

Innovation: To what extent the relevant contributions of the Deliverable can be considered novel and innovative? Does the Deliverable point out differences from related state-of-the-art issues? This question refers to the way that new problems or new approaches have been set up by the Deliverable – of course it cannot be applied to all Deliverables in ANIPH.

Soundness: How well supported are the conclusions drawn? All pieces of information, statements, claims, descriptions and conclusions should be strongly substantiated, and should be verified or traced to the appropriate sources of reference.

Consistency: Is the information included consistent with regards to other accepted statements, claims, descriptions and conclusions made elsewhere in ANIPH or, more generally, in the wider scientific and technical community?

References: Are the references adequate and necessary? This question refers to the appropriateness of the references used to concern the particular scope of the Deliverable.

- Format criteria

Readability: Comfortable and easy-reading, good use of vocabulary, grammar and orthography.

Terminology: All specific terms are adequately explained, in order to provide an appropriate frame of reference for the reader; a glossary might be included.

Structure: Which should be coherent and clearly organize different items and issues, while grouping together any appropriate elements.

Appearance: Formatting and physical distribution of images, tables and margins should be appealing and look professional. All Deliverables will be generated according to the common template that is included in the Project collaborative space and which has been used to write this Deliverable as well.

6 ANIPH online repository

ANIPH Online Repository (or ANIPH platform) is an internal, password-restricted web-based shared working environment, a Google Workspace platform created for CETEC as Project Coordinator for the ANIPH Project communication and information storage.

Only people assigned by ANIPH partners and registered by the Project Coordinator can access the ANIPH platform. When a partner needs to update (register or unregister) people on the platform, they must contact the Project Management Team who will guide them until access is complete. For this you can use the email coordination coordination@aniph.org

The following figures present the main structure and contents of the ANIPH platform.

Compartido conmigo > ANIPH Project ▾

Tipo ▾ Personas ▾ Modificado ▾

Nombre ↓	Propietario	Última modificación ▾
yo	14 nov 2024 yo	

Figure 5. ANIPH project Online Repository folders.

Compartido conmigo > ANIPH Project > Work Packages ▾

Nombre ↓	Propietario	Última modificación ▾
WP13_Ethics requirements	yo	14 nov 2024 yo
WP12_Communication, dissemination, exploitation and capacity bui...	yo	14 nov 2024 yo
WP11_ANIPH SSbD assessment and enabling conditions-2	yo	14 nov 2024 yo
WP10_Demonstration of ANIPH solution	yo	14 nov 2024 yo
WP9_End of life: Safe & sustainable biodegradation and recyclabilit...	yo	14 nov 2024 yo
WP8_Manufacturing of biodegradable wound dressing and packagi...	yo	14 nov 2024 yo
WP7_Project Management and coordination activities-2	yo	14 nov 2024 yo
WP6_Communication, dissemination and exploitation -baselines	yo	14 nov 2024 yo
WP5_ANIPH SSbD assessment and enabling conditions-1	yo	14 nov 2024 yo
WP4_Preliminary manufacturing of materials for wound dressing an...	yo	14 nov 2024 yo
WP3_Manufacturing of PHBV and PHN ranges programming the saf...	yo	14 nov 2024 yo
WP2_ANIPH project baseline	yo	14 nov 2024 yo
WP1_Project Management and coordination activities-1	yo	14 nov 2024 yo

Figure 6. ANIPH WPs folder content.

Compartido conmigo > ANIPH Project > Templates & Logos ▾

Nombre ↓	Propietario	Última modificación ▾
Website	yo	14 nov 2024 yo
Partners Logo	yo	14 nov 2024 yo
EU Logos	yo	14 nov 2024 yo
ANIPH Templates	yo	14 nov 2024 yo
ANIPH Logo	yo	14 nov 2024 yo

Figure 7. ANIPH templates and logos folder content.

Compartido conmigo > ANIPH Project > Official documents ▾

Tipo ▾ Personas ▾ Modificado ▾

Nombre ↓	Propietario	Última modificación ▾
yo	14 nov 2024 yo	

Figure 8. ANIPH official documents folder content.

7 ANIPH online work management system

ANIPH Online Work Flow Management is an internal, password-restricted web-based shared working environment, a Monday Workspace platform created by CETEC as Project Coordinator for planning, organizing, and tracking the tasks of the ANIPH Project in a collaboratively and efficiently way.

Only people assigned by ANIPH partners and registered by the Project Coordinator can access the ANIPH platform. When a partner needs to update (register or unregister) people on the platform, they must contact the Project Management Team who will guide them until access is complete. For this you can use the email coordination coordination@aniph.org

The following figures represent the main structure of the dashboards in ANIPH platform.

The Project Coordinator is the responsible for updating the platform data, including the contacts, meetings, objectives, Gantt, deliverables, and risks management. The Work Package leaders and the Tasks leaders are responsible for updating the work packages and tasks information periodically (at least quarterly).

Figure 9. ANIPH Monday platform structure

- > **WP1**
1 Element / 3 subelementos
- > **WP2**
1 Element / 10 subelementos
- > **WP3**
1 Element / 10 subelementos
- > **WP4**
1 Element / 9 subelementos
- > **WP5**
1 Element / 9 subelementos
- > **WP6**
1 Element / 6 subelementos
- > **WP7**
1 Element / 3 subelementos
- > **WP8**
1 Element / 12 subelementos
- > **WP9**
1 Element / 8 subelementos
- > **WP10**
1 Element / 9 subelementos
- > **WP11**
1 Element / 8 subelementos
- > **WP12**
1 Element / 4 subelementos
- > **WP13**
1 Element
- > **Deliverables**
13 Elements / 54 subelementos
- > **Objectives**
9 Elements
- > **Milestones**
16 Elements / 26 subelementos
- > **Foreseen Risks**
19 Elements / 1 subelemento
- > **Unforeseen Risks**
1 Element

Figure 10. ANIPH DOA dashboard structure on Monday.

Element	Schedule	State	Responsible	WP Leader	WP Leaders Emails
WP1 - Project Management and coordination activities-1	Jan 31, 25 - Dec 31, 26	Working on it	1 - CETEC	Verónica Alcaraz & Carmen Fernández	
Subitem	Schedule	State	Leader	Leader name	Others
T11. Project Coordination, Quality Assurance and Risk Management.	Jan 31, 25 - Dec 31, 26	Working on it	1 - CETEC	Verónica Alcaraz & Carmen Fernández	1 - CETEC, 2 - C...
T12. Administrative & Financial Coordination.	Jan 1, 25 - Dec 31, 26	Working on it	1 - CETEC	Juan Agüera	1 - CETEC, 2 - C...
T13. Data management plan and Ethical issues management	Jan 1, 25 - Dec 31, 26	Working on it	7 - KVC	Alba Matamoros	71 - KVC - ES

Figure 11. Overview to the structure at WP level.

Element	Schedule	State	Responsible	WP Leader	Task Leaders	WP Leader email
WP1	1 Jan, 25 - 31 Dec, 26	Not initiated	1 - CETEC	Verónica Alcaraz & Carmen Fernández	ALL	
WP2	1 Jan - 31 Dec	Not initiated	1 - CETEC	Jean David Peltier	5 - ... 7 - ... 3 - ...	
WP3	1 Mar, 25 - 30 Nov, 26	Not initiated	2 - CETBO	María Nicolosi & Salvador García	1 - CETEC 7 - KVC	
WP4	1 Jun, 26 - 31 Dec, 26	Not initiated	5 - UGR	Juan Antonio Marchal Comares & JM Do...	4 - TVB 3 - AUA	
WP5	1 Oct, 25 - 31 Dec, 26	Not initiated	7 - KVC	Alba Matamoros	1 - ... 7 - ... 6 - G...	
WP6	1 Jan, 25 - 31 Dec, 26	Not initiated	8 - ICONS	Marcello Bardellini & Chiara Seno	7 - KVC 1 - CETEC	
WP7	1 Dec, 26 - 31 Dec, 26	Not initiated	7 - KVC	Carmen Fernández & Verónica Alcaraz		
WP8	1 Dec, 26 - 31 Dec, 27	Not initiated	5 - UGR	Juan Antonio Marchal Comares	4 - TVB 3 - AUA	
WP9	1 Dec, 26 - 31 Dec, 26	Not initiated	3 - AUA	Chrysanthos Maraveas & Marianna Kotza...	1 - CETEC	
WP10	1 Jan, 26 - 31 Dec, 26	Not initiated	5 - UGR	Juan Antonio Marchal Comares & JM Do...	2 - C... 1 - ... 3 - ...	
WP11	1 Jan, 27 - 31 Dec, 26	Not initiated	7 - KVC	Alba Matamoros	1 - CETEC 3 - AUA	
WP12	1 Jan, 27 - 31 Dec, 26	Not initiated	8 - ICONS	Marcello Bardellini & Chiara Seno	7 - KVC	
WP13	1 Jan, 25 - 31 Dec, 26	Not initiated	1 - CETEC	Carmen Fernández & Verónica Alcaraz		

Element	Schedule	State	Responsible	WP Leader	Task Leaders	WP Leader email
WPI	1 ene., '25 - 31 dic., '26	Not initiated	1 - CETEC	Verónica Alcaraz & Carmen Fernández	ALL	
Subelemento	Schedule	State	WP Leader	Leader name	Others	
D1.1 Project management - R/PU	31 mar.	Not initiated	1 - CETEC	Verónica Alcaraz, Carmen Fernández & Juan Agüera	ALL	
D1.2 Preliminary Data Management Plan and Ethic handbook. - ...	30 jun.	Not initiated	7 - KVC	Alba Matamoros	7.1 - KVC - ES	
D1.3 Interim Data Management Plan. - DMP / PU	31 dic., '26	Not initiated	7 - KVC	Alba Matamoros	7.1 - KVC - ES	

Figure 12. Overview to the structure at deliverables level.

Element	Schedule	State	Responsible	Others	Emails	Dependency
SO1. To ensure circularity and programmed biodegradation through PHAs production processes	1 Mar. '25 - 31 Dec. '28	Not initiated	2 - CETBO	3 - AUA 5 - UGR		WP3 Manufacturing of PHAs SS M4 SS WP9 - End of life Saf... SS H1
SO2. To ensure programmed biodegradation through PHAs formulation and compounding	1 Mar. '25 - 31 Dec. '27	Not initiated	2 - CETBO	5 - UGR		M7 SS WP3 Manufacturing of PHAs SS WP6 - Manufacturing of... SS
SO3. To develop functional materials while supporting the programming of biodegradation	1 Mar. '25 - 30 Jun. '28	Not initiated	5 - UGR	2 - CETBO		M8 SS M13 SS WP3 Manufacturing of PHAs SS WP4 Preliminary... SS
SO4. To ensure circularity and programmed biodegradation through PHAs conversion processes	1 Oct. '25 - 31 Dec. '28	Not initiated	5 - UGR	7 - KVC		M10 SS M14 SS WP5 ANIPH SSBD assessment and enablin... SS
SO5. To demonstrate a reproducible biodegradation assessment in relevant environments	1 Mar. '25 - 31 Dec. '28	Not initiated	2 - CETBO	5 - UGR		WP3 Manufacturing of PHAs SS WP4 Preliminary manufact... SS H2
SO6. To demonstrate circular, safe and sustainable end-of life routes for ANIPH BtPs	1 Mar. '25 - 31 Dec. '28	Not initiated	2 - CETBO	5 - UGR 7 - KVC 3 - AUA		WP3 Manufacturing of PHAs SS WP8 - Manufac... SS M11 SS M5 SS H1
SO7. To develop tools supporting circularity and SSBD assessments	1 Jan. '25 - 31 Dec. '28	Working on it	7 - KVC	1 - CETEC 5 - UGR		WP5 ANIPH SSBD assess... SS WP11 ANIPH SSBD assess... SS H3
SO8. To ensure Safe & Sustainable ANIPH BtPs and create an enabling framework	1 Jan. '25 - 31 Dec. '28	Working on it	7 - KVC	3 - AUA 1 - CETEC 6 - ICONS		M15 SS WP9 - End... SS M2 SS M6 SS WP2 ANIP... SS
SO9. Maximizing project outputs and impacts	1 Jan. '25 - 31 Dec. '28	Working on it	8 - ICONS			WP6 Communic... SS WP12 Communic... SS M12 SS M16 SS

Figure 13. Overview to the structure at objectives level.

Element	Schedule	State	Responsible	WP Leader	Task Leaders	WP Leader email	Dependency
M1	30 Jun.	Not initiated	8 - ICONS	Marcello Bardellini & Chiara Senio			WP6 SS
M2	30 Sep.	Not initiated	1 - CETEC	Jean David Peltier	7 - KVC 6 - GOPHA		WP2 SS
M3	31 Dec.	Not initiated	1 - CETEC	Jean David Peltier	3 - AUA		WP2 SS
M4	30 Jun. '26	Not initiated	2 - CETBO	María Nicolás & Salvador García	1 - CETEC 7 - KVC		WP3 SS
M5	30 Jun. '26	Not initiated	7 - KVC	Alba Matamoros	1 - CETEC 3 - AUA		WP5 SS
M6	30 Jun. '26	Not initiated	8 - ICONS	Marcello Bardellini & Chiara Senio			WP6 SS
M7	30 Nov. '26	Not initiated	2 - CETBO	María Nicolás & Salvador García	1 - CETEC 7 - KVC		WP3 SS
M8	28 Feb. '27	Not initiated	5 - UGR	Juan Antonio Marchal Corrales			WP8 SS
M9	30 Jun. '27	Not initiated	7 - KVC	Alba Matamoros			WP11 SS
M10	31 Dec. '27	Not initiated	5 - UGR	Juan Antonio Marchal Corrales			WP8 SS
M11	31 Dec. '27	Not initiated	7 - KVC	Alba Matamoros			WP11 SS
M12	31 Dec. '27	Not initiated	8 - ICONS	Marcello Bardellini & Chiara Senio			WP9 SS
M13	30 Jun. '28	Not initiated	5 - UGR	Juan Antonio Marchal Corrales & JM Do...			WP10 SS
M14	31 Dec. '28	Not initiated	5 - UGR	Juan Antonio Marchal Corrales & JM Do...			WP9 SS WP10 SS
M15	31 Dec. '28	Not initiated	7 - KVC	Alba Matamoros			WP11 SS
M16	31 Dec. '28	Not initiated	8 - ICONS	Marcello Bardellini & Chiara Senio			WP12 SS

Figure 14. Overview to the structure at milestones level.

<p>> Foreseen Risks</p> <p>19 Elements / 1 Subitem</p>	<p>Schedule</p> <p>1 Jan, '25 - 31 Dec, '28</p>
<p>> Unforeseen Risks</p> <p>1 Element</p>	<p>Schedule</p> <p>-</p>

Foreseen Risks

Element	Schedule	State	Responsible	Others	Dependency
Risk 1 (T) Low-6 (1x6)	1 Jan - 31 Dec	Working on it	1 - CETEC	2 - CETBO	WP3: Manufacturing of PHBV and PHN; WP2: ANIPH project baseline
Risk 2 (T) Medium-8 (2x4)	1 Jan - 31 Dec	Working on it	1 - CETEC		WP2: ANIPH project baseline
Risk 3 (T) Low-6 (1x6)	1 Feb - 31 Dec	Working on it	2 - CETBO		WP3: Manufacturing of PHBV and PHN ranges programming the safe biodegrad...
Risk 4 (T) Medium-8 (2x4)	1 Jan - 31 Dec	Working on it	2 - CETBO		WP3: Manufacturing of PHBV and PHN ranges programming the safe biodegrad...
Risk 5 (T) Low-6 (1x6)	1 Jan - 31 Dec	Working on it	1 - CETEC		WP2: ANIPH project baseline
Risk 6 (T) Low-6 (1x6)	1 Jan, '26 - 31 Dec, '27	Not initiated	5 - UGR		WP8 - Manufacturing of biodeg...; WP4: Preliminary manufacturing...
Risk 7 (T) Low-6 (1x6)	1 Jan, '26 - 31 Dec, '27	Not initiated	5 - UGR		WP4: Preliminary manufacturing...; WP8 - Manufacturing of biodeg...
Risk 8 (T) Medium-8 (2x4)	1 Jan, '26 - 31 Dec, '27	Not initiated	5 - UGR		WP8 - Manufacturing of biodeg...; WP10 - Demonstration of ANIPH...
Risk 9 (T) Medium-8 (2x4)	1 Dec, '26 - 31 Dec, '28	Not initiated	5 - UGR		WP8 - Manufacturing of biodeg...; WP10 - Demonstration of ANIPH...
Risk 10 (T) Medium-8 (2x4)	1 Feb, '27 - 31 Dec, '28	Not initiated	5 - UGR	2 - CETBO, 3 - AJA, 1 - CETEC, 7 - KVC	WP8 - Manufacturing of biodeg...; WP10 - Demonstration of A...
Risk 11 (T) Medium-8 (2x4)	1 Jan, '27 - 31 Dec, '28	Not initiated	3 - AJA		WP9 - End of life: Safe & sustainable biodegradation and recyclability val...
Risk 12 (S) Low-6 (1x6)	1 Oct, '27 - 31 Dec, '28	Not initiated	7 - KVC		WPS ANIPH SSSD assessment...; WP11 ANIPH SSSD assessment...
Risk 13 (S) Low-6 (1x6)	1 Jan, '28 - 31 Dec, '28	Working on it	7 - KVC		WP11 ANIPH SSSD assessment and enabling conditions 2...
Risk 14 (S) Medium-8 (2x4)	1 Oct, '28 - 31 Dec, '28	Not initiated	7 - KVC		WPS ANIPH SSSD assessment...; WP11 ANIPH SSSD assessment...
Risk 15 (E) Medium-8 (2x4)	1 Jan, '29 - 31 Dec, '28	Working on it	8 - ICONS		WP8: Communication, dissemination...; WP12: Communication, dissemin...
Risk 16 (E) Medium-8 (2x4)	1 Jan, '27 - 31 Dec, '28	Not initiated	8 - ICONS		WP12: Communication, dissemination, exploitation and capacity building...
Risk 17 (M) Low-6 (1x6)	1 Jan, '27 - 31 Dec, '28	Not initiated	1 - CETEC	4 - ICONS	WP7: Project Man...; WP1 - Project Man...; WP5: Communicat...
Risk 18 (M) Low-6 (1x6)	1 Jan, '27 - 31 Dec, '28	Not initiated	1 - CETEC		WP1 - Project Management and...; WP7: Project Management and...
Risk 19 (M) Medium-8 (2x4)	1 Jan, '27 - 31 Dec, '28	Not initiated	1 - CETEC		WP1 - Project Management and...; WP7: Project Management and...

Figure 15. Overview of the structure at risks level.

Deliverables Review Plan

Agregar deliverables

Deliverables	Type / Dissemination Level	Link deliverable	1st Due Da.	1 - State	1 - Responsible Partner	1 - Responsible people	1 - Email	2nd Due date	2 - State	Reviewer Partner 1
D1.1 Project management	Report / Public		3 mar.	Working on it	1 - CETEC	Verónica Alcaraz & Mamen Fernández		10 mar.		7 - KVC
D1.2 Preliminary Data Management Plan and Ethic handbook	DHP / Public		30 may.		7 - KVC	Alba Matamoros		6 jun.		8 - ICONS
D1.3 Interim Data Management Plan.	DHP / Public		23 nov., 2026		7 - KVC	Alba Matamoros		30 nov., 2026		8 - ICONS
D2.1 ANIPH requirements	Report / Sensative	https://docs.google...	14 feb.	Working on it	1 - CETEC	Jean David Peltier		21 feb.		6 - GORHA
D2.2 ELs mapping	Report / Public		2 sep.		6 - GORHA	Rick Passanier		9 sep.		1 - CETEC
D2.3 ANIPH SSSD framework	Report / Public		31 mar.		7 - KVC	Alba Matamoros		7 abr.		2 - CETBO
D2.4 ANIPH raw materials and additives.	Report / Sensative		24 nov.		1 - CETEC	Jean David Peltier		1 dic.		6 - GORHA
D2.5 ANIPH AI predictive tool.	OTHER / Public		24 nov.		3 - AJA	Chrysanthos Maraveas, Marianna Kol...		1 dic.		5 - UGR
D2.6 Non-sensitive ICT Platform	OTHER / Public		24 nov.		1 - CETEC	Jaime Ortiz		1 dic.		5 - UGR
D2.7 Sensitive ICT Platform	OTHER / Sensative		24 nov.		1 - CETEC	Jaime Ortiz		1 dic.		5 - UGR
D2.8 ANIPH Data libraries	Report / Public		24 nov.		3 - AJA	Chrysanthos Maraveas, Marianna Kol...		1 dic.		5 - UGR
D3.1 PHBV and PHN ranges production with programmed bi...	Report / Sensative		29 may., 2026		2 - CETBO	Salvador Garcia		5 jun.		1 - CETEC
D3.2 PHBV& PHN formulation and compounding	Report / Sensative		29 may., 2026		1 - CETEC	Jean David Peltier		5 jun.		3 - AJA
D3.3 First AI predictive assessment.	Report / Sensative		29 may., 2026		3 - AJA	Chrysanthos Maraveas, Marianna Kol...		5 jun.		5 - UGR
D3.4 PHBV and PHN compounds optimisation.	Report / Sensative		29 may., 2026		1 - CETEC	Jean David Peltier		5 jun.		3 - AJA

Figure 16. Overview of the deliverables review plan.

8 Other relevant information

English is the official language in ANIPH. All documents must be written in English. Nevertheless, there can be exceptions with some dissemination materials, such as press releases or even technical publications of national reach, which can – if needed – be translated to other languages.

9 Conclusions

Deliverable 1.1, “Project Management”, serves as a foundational guideline for the ANIPH Consortium, establishing robust project management procedures and a comprehensive quality framework. This deliverable effectively outlines the project's governance structures, clearly defining the roles and responsibilities of governance bodies, operational procedures, and scheduled meetings. By providing standardized templates and detailed information flow diagrams, Deliverable 1.1 ensures consistent communication and efficient knowledge sharing amongst consortium partners. Furthermore, the established deliverable review plan guarantees the quality and coherence of all project outputs.

The defined internal procedures and decision-making mechanisms within this plan are designed to foster seamless communication and collaboration, thereby significantly contributing to the successful achievement of the project's objectives.

It is crucial to emphasize that Deliverable 1.1 operates in conjunction with other key reference documents, including the Grant Agreement, Annex I (Description of Action) Parts A and B, and the Consortium Agreement. These documents collectively provide the legal and operational framework necessary for the effective implementation of the ANIPH project. The adherence to the guidelines outlined in Deliverable 1.1, in conjunction with these reference documents, will ensure the project's alignment with the European Commission's expectations and facilitate the delivery of high-quality results.

10 References

The following documents have been necessary to develop the deliverable 1.1. “Project Management”:

- ANIPH DoA, which is Annex 1 to the Grant Agreement Number 101181943, and contains the details of how the action (project) will be carried out. This document was prepared during the initiating and planning phase of the project.
- ANIPH Grant Agreement Number 101181943.
- ANIPH Consortium agreement.
- PM² Project Management Methodology Guide 3.0.1, March 2021.
- PM² Glossary based on the PM² Guide v3.0.

11 Annexes

Meeting Agenda Template

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101181943.

Meeting Agenda

Meeting Title:		Meeting Date/Time:	
Meeting Type:		Meeting Location:	
Meeting Organizer:			

Participant Name <i>(invited)</i>	Organisation / Email

Meeting Objectives
1.

Agenda Items	Time	Owner

Related Documents	Location
XYZ.doc	U:\ProjectX\Documents

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101181943.

<Document Name coding: AoM_XX_DDMMYY>

XX	Type of meeting
GA	General Assembly
PMB	Project Management Board
AB	Advisory Board
WP1	Work package 1
WP2	Work package 2
WP3	Work package 3
WP4	Work package 4
WP5	Work package 5
WP6	Work package 6
WP7	Work package 7
WP8	Work package 8
OTHER	Other type of meeting

DD	Day
MM	Month in number
YY	Year

Minutes of Meeting Agenda Template

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Minutes of Meeting

Meeting Title:		Meeting Date/Time:	
Meeting Type:		Meeting Location:	
Meeting Organizer:			Issue Date:

Attendee Name	Organisation / Email	Online/In Person

Meeting Agenda

Meeting Summary

Decisions taken			
Decision Id	Description	Date of Decision Taken	Decision Owner
		<i>dd/mm/yy</i>	<i>Initials</i>

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Actions / To Do Items					
Action Id	Creation Date	Description	Status	Target Resolution Date	Owner
	<i>dd/mm/yy</i>		<i>Open</i>	<i>dd/mm/yy</i>	<i>Initials</i>
			<i>In Progress</i>		
			<i>Closed</i>		
			<i>On Hold</i>		

Proposed Agenda for Next Meeting	Proposed Next Meeting Date:
<i>List potential agenda items of the next meeting</i>	

Related Documents	Location
XYZ.doc	U:\ProjectX\Documents

<Document Name coding: MoM_XX_DDMMYY>

XX	Type of meeting
GA	General Assembly
PMB	Project Management Board
AB	Advisory Board
WPX	Work package x
OTHER	Other type of meeting

DD	Day
MM	Month in number
YY	Year

Change Request Form Template

ANIPH_Change_Request_Form_DDMMYY

ANIPH

Change Request Form

WP/TASK	< WP&Task ID>	Change ID:	<link to the change log>						
<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px;"> <div style="background-color: #cccccc; padding: 2px;">Change Request</div> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%;">Change Title:</td> <td style="width: 50%;">Identification Date: <dd/mm/yyyy></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Requested by: <The name of the requestor/group></td> <td>Category:</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="2"> Priority: <input type="checkbox"/> Very High <input type="checkbox"/> High <input type="checkbox"/> Medium <input type="checkbox"/> Low <input type="checkbox"/> Very Low </td> </tr> </table> <div style="background-color: #cccccc; padding: 2px; margin-top: 5px;">Change Description & Details</div> <p style="color: #0070c0; font-size: small; margin-top: 5px;"><The purpose of this form is to capture the need and characteristics of a project change request. The change request is the first step of the change request process. Once the change request is logged into the Change Log, then this form is updated with the assigned Change ID and the form is archived.></p> <p>Current Situation: <Describe the current situation (a problem, an opportunity or a new need – why is there a need for a change in the project?)></p> <p>Desired Situation: < Describe the desired situation. What is the goal and benefits of this change request?></p> <p>Impact or Risks: <Describe the impact or risks of not implementing this change. If this impact or risks can be quantified, then this can help with the analysis (cost benefit analysis) and final decision regarding the implementation (or not) and the priority of this change.></p> <p>Out of Scope: <Clarify what is out of the scope of this change request. This clarifies further the boundaries of the requested change and ensures that only the needed change is implemented.></p> </div>				Change Title:	Identification Date: <dd/mm/yyyy>	Requested by: <The name of the requestor/group>	Category:	Priority: <input type="checkbox"/> Very High <input type="checkbox"/> High <input type="checkbox"/> Medium <input type="checkbox"/> Low <input type="checkbox"/> Very Low	
Change Title:	Identification Date: <dd/mm/yyyy>								
Requested by: <The name of the requestor/group>	Category:								
Priority: <input type="checkbox"/> Very High <input type="checkbox"/> High <input type="checkbox"/> Medium <input type="checkbox"/> Low <input type="checkbox"/> Very Low									
References and Related Documents		Location							
XYZ.doc		U:\ProjectX\Documents\							

Task Status Report Template

SR_WPX_TaskX.Y_Quarter X Year

WP-TASK Status Report Quarter X

Identification: (SR_WPX_TaskX.Y_Quarter X Year)

Title:

Task Leader:

1. Objectives of activities undertaken in the task during the month

Provide a short summary of progress towards the achievement of each of the project objectives. Highlight significant activities in support of these achievements.

Assess to what extent the objectives of the project have been achieved.

2. Activities undertaken during the quarter

Explain the work carried out in the task during the month giving details of the work carried out by each beneficiary/affiliated entity involved.

Please describe activities compared to the initial planning specified in the DOA, including the partners involved. If there are deviations, please explain the reasons for them and corresponding corrective action taken.

3. Changes and difficulties arising during the month

Indicate any difficulties found during the [tasks](#) execution.

Please outline any change or corrective/contingency actions required. Indicate if there are changes in project action compared to the DoA. It includes changes linked to the activities, and resources (including budget, personnel involved, person month), other costs. Included [a](#) explanation of the impact of the changes on the planned work and the corrective actions planned.

4. Risk Identification and analysis

4.1.1 Foreseen risks

Complete the risks and mitigation actions identified in the DOA that have been relevant.

Risk No	Reporting period	Did the risk materialised?	Did you apply risk mitigation measures?
[Risk number]	[RP number]	[YES/NO]	[YES/NO]. If yes, explain them

Task status report_template v.0

Page 1 de 2

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SK_WPA_TaskX.Y_Quarter X Year

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4.1.2 Unforeseen risks

Please, include the new risks identified, if any, and the proposed mitigation measures.

Risk description	Rank (Low/Medium/High)	Mitigation measures

5. Innovation: IP/Results

RESULTS	Description	Exploitable/not exploitable

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WP Status Report Template

WPX Status Report Quarter X

Identification: (WPX_Status Report_QuarterX)

Title:

WP Leader:

Document history

V	Date	Comments
v0.1		First version of the document sent by the ANIPH Manager to the Project Coordination Team
v1.0		Version reviewed (including changes, if necessary) by the Project Coordination Team
v1.x		Other version reviewed by the Project Coordination Team, if necessary.

1. Objectives of activities undertaken during the last quarter

Provide a short summary of progress towards the achievement of each of the project objectives. Highlight significant activities in support of these achievements.

Assess to what extent the objectives of the project have been achieved.

2. Activities undertaken during the last quarter

Explain the work carried out in the WP during the month giving details of the work carried out in each task by each beneficiary/affiliated entity involved.

Please describe activities compared to the initial planning specified in the DoA, including the partners involved. If there are deviations, please explain the reasons for them and corresponding corrective action taken.

3. Changes and difficulties arising during the last quarter

Indicate any difficulties found during the work package execution.

Please outline any change or corrective/contingency actions required. Indicate if there are changes in project action compared to the DoA. It includes changes linked to the activities, and resources (including budget, personnel involved, person month), other costs. Included an explanation of the impact of the changes on the planned work and the corrective actions planned.

WPX_Status Report Quarter X. ANIPH. vx.x

4. Risk Identification and analysis

4.1.1 Foreseen risks

Complete the risks and mitigation actions identified in the DOA that have been relevant during the work package.

Risk No	Reporting period	Did the risk materialised?	Did you apply risk mitigation measures?
[Risk number]	[RP number]	[YES/NO]	[YES/NO]. If yes, explain them

4.1.2 Unforeseen risks

Please, include the new risks identified, if any, and the proposed mitigation measures.

Risk description	Rank (Low/Medium/High)	Mitigation measures

5. Project Deliverables Status

Deliverable number	% completed	Expected submission date	Submission date	Reason for delay (if any)

6. Innovation: IP/Results

RESULTS	Description	Exploitable/not exploitable

WP Summary Report Template

WPX_Year -Summary for the reporting period x (month xx to month xx)

WPX Summary for the reporting period X (month x to month x)

Identification: (WPX Summary_PRx-Year)

Title:

WP Leader:

1. Objectives of activities undertaken during the periodic report

Provide a short summary of progress towards the achievement of each of the project objectives. Highlight significant activities in support of these achievements.

Please provide clear and measurable details. Assess to what extent the objectives of the project for the period have been achieved in relation to the DoA. |

OBJECTIVE X (linked to WPX)	Complete the objective as DOA
Work carried out towards its achievement:	

2. Work performed and main activities undertaken during the periodic report

2.1 Work Plan

Explain the work carried out in the WP during the reporting period giving details of the work carried out in each task by each beneficiary/affiliated entity involved.

Please describe activities and the main achievements compared to the initial planning specified in the DOA. If there are deviations, please explain them.

For each work package (WP)

- o *explain the progress in relation to the DoA (including the achievement of deliverables and milestones) and periodic report*
- o *explain any deviation and/or delays, the reasons for them and corresponding corrective action taken.*
- o *explain whether the pilots/case studies started to showcase innovative results as described in the DoA (results achieved and at what level providing a clear description of tangible innovative results).*

WPX: Title		WP Leader: XX.
Month xxx to Month XXX	Completion: XX%	
Objectives:		

WP summary for the PRX v.0

Page 1 de 6

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WPX_Year -Summary for the reporting period x (month xx to month xx)

Risk description	Rank (Low/Medium/High)	Mitigation measures

4. Project Deliverables Status

Deliverable number	% completed	Expected submission date	Submission date	Reason for delay (if any)

5. Impact

5.1 Explain how the work carried out contribute to the expected impacts detailed in the DoA.

Describe the progress of the project so far towards delivering scientific impact, based on its objectives and towards delivering impact in any of the following fields (if applicable): scientific, economic, societal or industrial production or processes. Report on changes to the expected impacts presented in your DoA and the effects on the project/need for adaptations.

Where necessary, provide further details of your monitoring and evaluation strategy, including: references to baselines, benchmarks, assumptions used (with justification) as well as calculations performed to quantify the impacts.

Please, include the status of the impacts as follow: not achieved, partially achieved, achieved.

5.2. Explain how the work carried out contribute to enhance innovation capacity, create new markets opportunities, strengthen competitiveness and growth of companies, address issues related to climate change or the environment, address industrial and/or societal needs at regional level or bring other important benefits for society.

Please, give information on the relevant innovation activities carried out (prototypes, testing activities, standards, clinical trials) and/or new product, service, reference materials, process or method (to be) launched to the market, if any.

WPX_Year -Summary for the reporting period x (month xx to month xx)

5.3 Explain how the work carried out contribute to the European policies and strategies.

Please, explain if the project results or activities can have an impact on policies, like those concerning healthcare, environment, energy, regional development, etc. by supporting policy implementation, policy stakeholder engagement or exploring new technological approaches for policy objectives, for example. The project can, if applicable, present its findings to policy makers or include policy makers in an advisory board.

6. Update of the plan for exploitation and dissemination of results

Complete the partner responsible of the exploitation and dissemination.

Include in this section any updates to the plan for exploitation and dissemination of results and give details about its execution.

Please, explain the project results disseminated in scientific publications, including the deposition of publications in open access repositories and their reference to EU funding.

Please, explain how the beneficiaries disseminated and communicated project activities and results by other means than scientific publications (as press, social media, the project web site, video) and their reference to EU funding.

Please, explain the plan for exploitation of results and how the intellectual property rights have been managed. Complete the table:

IP RESULTS	Description	Exploitable/not exploitable

7. Update of the data management plan and ethics

Complete the partner responsible of the data management plan and ethics.

Please, explain details about the data management plan, update and execution.

Please, explain how the ethics deliverables and/or requirements for the current period have been adequately addressed.

8. Deviations from Annex 1 and Annex to from the DOA

8.1 Tasks

Include deviations occurred in the work package during the reporting period in the following table.

WP summary for the PRX v.0

Page 4 de 6

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WPX_Year -Summary for the reporting period x (month xx to month xx)

Task name	Lead beneficiary	Deviation description	Impact on the planned work	Corrective actions

8.2 Use of resources

8.2.1. Budget

Please, if there are deviations from planned budget explain them clearly.

8.2.2 Person month

Include the number of person month planned in the DoA and the number of person month actually worked (during this reporting period) in the work package per each partner.

Please in case of deviation include an explanation.

Beneficiary number /name	WPX person month	
	DoA	Reporting period

8.2.3 Other costs

Please, include changes, if any, linked to other costs (e.g. change of equipment).

9. Follow up of recommendations and comments from previous review

Please, include how you have accomplished with the recommendations from previous review (if applicable).

WPX_Year -Summary for the reporting period x (month xx to month xx)

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Deliverable Template

Document title/D#.#

WP #, T #.#

Authors: Author1 (Partner short name); Author2 (Partner short name)

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Technical references

Project Acronym	ANIPH
Project Title	Avoiding the Negative Impacts produced by Plastic materials in Humanitarian contexts
Project Coordinator	ASOCIACION EMPRESARIAL DE INVESTIGACION CENTRO TECNOLÓGICO DEL CALZADO Y DEL PLÁSTICO DE LA REGIÓN DE MURCIA CETEC Carmen Fernández: c.fernandez@ctcalzado.org
Project Duration	January 2025 – December 2028 (48 months)

Deliverable No.	D#.#
Dissemination level*	
Work Package	WP # - WP Title
Task	T#.# - Task Title
Lead beneficiary	Partner number (partner short name)
Contributing beneficiary/ies	Partner number (partner short name), Partner number (partner short name), Partner number (partner short name)...
Due date of deliverable	DD Month 201Y
Actual submission date	DD Month 201Y

- *PU – Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page)
- SEN – Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
- Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444
- Classified C-UE/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444
- Classified S-UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

V	Date	Comments	Author
V0	23/23/2023	First draft of document	Lorem ipsum
V1		Revised version based on the comments of the internal reviewer 1	
V2		Revised version based on the comments of the internal reviewer 1	
VF		Final version, approved by the project coordinator and submitted to EC	

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1. Table of contents

1. Table of contents.....	3
2. List of abbreviations	5
3. Executive Summary	6
4. Introduction	7
5. My first Section (Title 1 style)	8
5.1. My first Chapter (Title 2 style)	8
5.1.1. My first Subchapter (Title 3 style).....	8
5.1.2. Second subchapter.....	8
5.2. Second chapter	9
6. Conclusions	10
7. References	11
8. Annexes.....	13

List of Tables

Table 1: lorem ipsum	8
Table 2: lorem ipsum dolor	8

List of Figures

Figure 1: lorem ipsum	9
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2. List of abbreviations

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3. Executive Summary

[This section must be a summary of the work done and results obtained rather than an introduction, to anticipate the deliverable content and facilitate its comprehension by an external reviewer]

[Especially in the case of deliverables related to technological findings, research contexts and impact assessments, this summary must include Key points, findings, recommendations and conclusions]

[In the case of public deliverables, synthesis must be done for laymen's understanding]

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4. Introduction

[This section must provide a foundational explanation or background to guide through the subsequent content, it should serve to put the deliverable in context in the overall project, its objectives and the problem it addresses, providing solid links with other part of the research and other project tasks]

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5. My first Section (Title 1 style)

[In this section includes the deliverable description]

[For technical deliverables include a section related to the evaluation of results: the results' significance, explain the state of the art before ANIPH intervention and how the project brought it forward, compared to the current state of the art.]

5.1. My first Chapter (Title 2 style)

5.1.1. My first Subchapter (Title 3 style)

Body text (Normal style): **Lorem Ipsum** is simply dummy text of the printing and typesetting industry. Lorem Ipsum has been the industry's standard dummy text ever since the 1500s, when an unknown printer took a galley of type and scrambled it to make a type specimen book. It has survived not only five centuries, but also the leap into electronic typesetting, remaining essentially unchanged. It was popularised in the 1960s with the release of Letraset sheets containing Lorem Ipsum passages, and more recently with desktop publishing software like Aldus PageMaker including versions of Lorem Ipsum.

Table 1: lorem ipsum

	Lorem	Ipsum	Dolor	Sit Amet	Sententiam
Nullit	12	12	12	12	12
Repsius	12	12	12	12	12

5.1.2. Second subchapter

It has survived not only five centuries, but also the leap into electronic typesetting, remaining essentially unchanged. It was popularised in the 1960s with the release of Letraset sheets containing Lorem Ipsum passages, and more recently with desktop publishing software like Aldus PageMaker including versions of Lorem Ipsum.

Table 2: lorem ipsum dolor

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6. Conclusions

[This section should include a clear discussion of the final results. We should summarize challenges and how we have addressed them, highlighting how the outcomes contribute to the project objectives/milestones and to the “impacts” included in the DoA. We should also mention important activities carried out for the dissemination of the results (congresses, publications, posters).]

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7. References

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8. Annexes

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